

A Systematic Analysis of Structural and Theoretical Trends in Nepotism Research

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Abstract

This study presents a bibliometric analysis of scientific publications in the WoS and Scopus databases using the keyword "nepotism." A systematic content analysis was applied to evaluate the theoretical and methodological orientations of the literature. The aim of the study is to reveal the structure, geographical distribution, research trends, and main themes of academic output on nepotism. The analysis results show that nepotism is extensively addressed in multidisciplinary fields such as social sciences, business, economics, psychology, and political science. The prominence of concepts such as "corruption," "favoritism," and "family business" in Scopus data reflects the research focus on nepotism in institutional and ethical contexts, while the prevalence of terms such as "organizational justice" and "ethical value" in WoS data emphasizes the importance of social and ethical perspectives. When the geographical distribution is examined, the USA, the United Kingdom, China, and South Africa are in the leading positions in terms of publication volume and citation rates. In systematic content analysis, 43.8% of the studies were based on an ethical climate approach, 66.7% used quantitative methods, and 79.1% preferred one-dimensional measurement. In terms of nepotism types, studies based on kinship stood out, while 59.5% of the findings associated nepotism with negative consequences. It was observed that research in the field of nepotism has increased quantitatively and gained interdisciplinary diversity; however, there are shortcomings in conceptual clarity, methodological diversity, and comparative studies specific to different geographies.

Keywords: Organizational Behavior, Nepotism, Favoritism

JEL Codes:M12, M14, D73

Introduction

Nepotism is a socio-cultural phenomenon that manifests as individuals granting privileges to family members or close associates without regard to merit (Bayrakci, 2019; Çelik, 2024); historically, it has had an impact on many areas such as politics, economics, academia, and public administration (Schilpzand et al., 2024). This concept, originating from the Latin word nepos (grandson, nephew) (Ignatowski et al., 2020; Momand, 2020), is increasingly being questioned in modern societies in the context of unethical practices (Ferasso et al., 2025; Hassan et al., 2022), governance issues, and violations of social justice (Anand et al., 2025; Aytar & Çil, 2025). The presence of nepotism in corporate structures has the potential to directly affect key parameters such as governance quality, social trust, organizational performance, and employee motivation (Mbulaheni Ndou & Tthey Agbenyegah, 2024; Neamah et al., 2024; Olala, 2020).

The main objective of this study is to reveal the current state of academic output on nepotism; to analyze prominent thematic trends and research gaps. To this end, studies indexed in the Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) databases with the keyword "nepotism"

up to 2024 were examined using bibliometric methods. Bibliometric analysis is a highly effective method for visualizing the scientific development of a concept, collaboration networks among researchers, geographical distribution, and prominent conceptual relationships in the literature using quantitative data (Abdurahman et al., 2025; Handayani et al., 2024; Kaushal et al., 2021; Rahmah & Hamdi, 2022; Wahab et al., 2024).

The analysis primarily examined the distribution of publications in the WoS and Scopus databases by year, country, institution, author, and collaboration structure. Publications were classified according to their subject areas, and interdisciplinary concentrations were evaluated. According to Scopus data, the most frequently published fields are social science disciplines such as Business, Management and Accounting (279); Arts and Humanities (252); and Economics, Econometrics and Finance (225). In the WoS categories, Management (131), Economics (108), Business (91), and Political Science (64) were prominent research areas. Nepotism appears to be a significant research topic, particularly in the dimensions of organizational behavior, public policies, and corporate governance.

Keyword analyses revealed that the concepts most frequently associated with nepotism are themes such as "corruption," "cronyism," "favoritism," "family business," "organizational justice," and "governance." The study visualized the thematic structure of the nepotism literature in detail through conceptual maps created based on the co-occurrence relationships between keywords. Furthermore, the most cited publications and their contributing authors were identified; and prominent countries and institutions in academic output were analyzed using geographical maps.

This study aims not only to reveal the quantitative development of the nepotism literature through bibliometric indicators, but also to analyze the theoretical, methodological, and normative orientations of the literature through systematic content analysis performed on selected high-impact studies. Publications identified through bibliometric analysis were coded and classified according to the type of nepotism, theoretical basis, methodological approach, measurement method, and normative orientation of the findings. The aim is to provide an evaluation that reveals not only the structural size of the literature but also its epistemological and conceptual structure.

This research aims to contribute to both theoretical and applied literature by systematically analyzing the interdisciplinary nature of nepotism, its global trends, and research orientations through quantitative mapping and content-based analysis. The findings are expected to highlight the theoretical fragmentation surrounding nepotism and provide a conceptual framework for future qualitative and quantitative research. This study aims to reveal the quantitative development of the nepotism literature through bibliometric indicators, while also analyzing the theoretical, methodological, and normative orientations of the literature through systematic content analysis of selected high-impact studies. In this context, core publications identified through bibliometric analysis are coded and classified according to type of nepotism, theoretical basis, methodological approach, measurement method, and normative orientation of the findings. The study also aims to reveal the structural size, epistemological, and conceptual structure of the literature. The study aims to contribute to both theoretical and applied literature. This study systematically analyzes the interdisciplinary nature of nepotism, its global trends, and research orientations by combining quantitative mapping with content-based analysis.

1. Research Methodology

This study was designed using a bibliometric method to conduct a systematic analysis of academic publications on nepotism. Bibliometric analyses were used to create a structural and thematic map of research areas by evaluating publication trends, conceptual developments, citation and collaboration patterns in the literature. Clarivate Analytics' Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection and Elsevier's Scopus databases were used as resources

to comprehensively examine the interdisciplinary and global perspective of academic studies on nepotism. Data collection was carried out by searching for the keyword "nepotism" in the fields of title, abstract, and keywords. In both databases, the research was limited to social sciences-focused disciplines; publications in natural sciences, engineering, and technical sciences were excluded from the scope of the study. In this context, a total of 1,142 publications in the Scopus database and 1,079 publications in the WoS database were deemed suitable for analysis. The dataset included articles, reviews, books, and conference proceedings from the academic publication types. Publications written in English and Turkish were considered; sources in other languages were not included. The data analysis process involved the disciplinary classification of publications, the most cited publications and their impact, keywords, authors, and the visualization of network relationships between countries. Bibliometric software, specifically VOSviewer, was used to visualize keyword co-occurrence maps, country-based research collaborations, and network connections between authors. VOSviewer allows for network-based representation of bibliometric data, enabling the analysis of conceptual structures through thematic clusters.

In citation analysis, the most cited publications and authors were identified, and comparisons were made between databases. Citation data was obtained directly from databases, and current citation numbers as of the analysis date were used. This comparative citation analysis contributed to identifying pioneering studies and influential researchers in the field of nepotism.

In addition to the bibliometric analysis process, systematic content analysis was also applied in the study. Within this scope, 153 studies were selected from among publications with high citation rates and indexed in the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-E) and Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) from the bibliometric dataset using purposive sampling. The aim of this selection was to deeply examine the theoretical and methodological orientations of the literature through a sample representing current and influential publications in the nepotism literature. In the content analysis, the coding unit was determined as the article; each study was analyzed by evaluating its title, author keywords, Keywords Plus, and abstract text together. In the coding process, five main categories were considered: type of nepotism (kinship-based, political, academic, family business-based), theoretical basis (organizational justice, social change theory, social capital approach, institutionalism, ethical climate), methodological approach (quantitative, qualitative, mixed), measurement method (unidimensional, multidimensional), and normative orientation of the findings (negative, conditional, functional/positive). The coding process was conducted by two independent researchers, and inter-coder agreement was assessed using Cohen's Kappa coefficient. (Cohen, 1960). The Kappa coefficient is preferred as a reliability indicator in content analysis because it controls for random agreement in categorical classifications. (Silva et al., 2010; Yilmaz & Demirhan, 2023; Yu, Qian, & Li, 2024). Studies with differences among coders were re-examined, and a final codebook was developed through consensus. This analysis aims to go beyond bibliometric findings and comprehensively reveal the theoretical framework, methodological tendencies, and normative orientation of the nepotism literature.

2. Findings

Publications in the databases are classified by field, and the number of publications in each category and their ratio to the total number of publications are visualized in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Categorical Distribution of Publications on Nepotism in the WoS Database. In the WoS database, publications on nepotism are predominantly found in the fields of “Management” (12.14%), “Economics” (10.01%), and “Business” (8.43%); followed by disciplines specific to social sciences such as “Political Science”, “Public Administration”, and “Social Sciences Interdisciplinary”. A total of 1,079 publications were examined via WoS.

Figure 2: Categorical Distribution of Publications on Nepotism in the Scopus Database. In the Scopus database, the majority of studies on nepotism are concentrated in the fields of “Business, Management and Accounting” (24.43%), “Arts and Humanities” (22.07%), and “Economics, Econometrics and Finance” (19.70%). In addition, a significant number of publications are found in other important disciplines of the social sciences, such as “Psychology” (8.32%). In total, 1,142 publications were analyzed within this scope.

Both databases show that nepotism is addressed across various disciplines of the social sciences and examined from an interdisciplinary perspective. This distribution indicates that nepotism is not only researched in business management or economics, but also extensively across different disciplines of the social sciences such as sociology, psychology, and political science.

An examination of the most cited publications with the keyword "nepotism" in the WoS and Scopus databases reveals that both databases contain many collaborative studies that form the cornerstones of the literature. In particular, publications such as Pérez-González (2006), Thornhill and Gangestad (1993), Lee et al. (2003), Vanhanen (1999), and Jaskiewicz et al. (2013) are among the top 10 most cited publications in both WoS and Scopus. These collaborative studies have made significant contributions to nepotism research, both theoretically and practically.

When examining citation numbers, it is observed that the citation counts in the Scopus database are generally higher than those in WoS. This difference stems from Scopus's broader collection of journals in the social sciences, its coverage of more disciplines and international publications, and its more frequent updating of citation data. In contrast, the WoS database has a more selective scope, focusing on classical and high-impact journals. There are also important studies that appear in one database but not the other. For example, Wennerås and Wold's (1997) highly cited article, "Nepotism and Sexism in Peer Review," is listed in the WoS database, but not in the Scopus database. Similarly, Bowen et al.'s (2012) study on corruption and Duflo et al.'s (2015) research on educational governance, both listed in Scopus, are not included in the WoS's most cited publications list.

This difference stems from the indexing policies of the two databases, the diversity of journals they cover, and their update frequency. Generally, using both the WoS and Scopus databases together allows for a more comprehensive and in-depth analysis of the literature in the field of nepotism. Table 1 presents a comparative analysis of the data from both databases used in our study.

Table 1: Comparative List of the Most Cited Publications on "Nepotism" in the WoS and Scopus Databases.

Publication Status	Year	Author(s)	Title	Journal Name	WoS Citation	Scopus Citation
Co-Publications	1993	Thornhill, R.; Gangestad, S.W.	Human facial beauty – Averageness, symmetry and parasite resistance	Human Nature	445	518
	1999	Vanhane n, T.	Domestic ethnic conflict and ethnic nepotism	Journal of Peace Research	177	205
	2006	Pérez-González, F.	Inherited control and firm performance	American Economic Review	595	697
	2003	Lee, K.S.; vd.	Family business succession	Academy of Management Review	218	279
	2013	Jaskiewicz, P. vd.	Is nepotism good or bad? Types of nepotism and knowledge management	Family Business Review	156	187
WoS	1997	Wennerås, C.; Wold, A.	Nepotism and sexism in peer-review	Nature	838	—
	2014	Talhelm, T. vd.	Large-scale psychological differences... rice vs wheat agriculture	Science	828	—
	2011	Ceci, S.J.; Williams, W.M.	Understanding current causes of women's underrepresentation in science	PNAS	664	—

	1993	De Vries, M.F.R.K.	The dynamics of family controlled firms	Organizational Dynamics	434	—
	2012	van Arensbergen, vd.	Gender differences in scientific productivity	Scientometrics	164	—
Scopus	2012	Bowen, P.A. vd.	Corruption in the South African construction industry	Construction Management and Economics	—	143
	2004	Islam, N.	Sifarish, sycophants, power and collectivism in Pakistan	International Review of Administrative Sciences	—	144
	2015	Duflo, E. vd.	School governance and teacher incentives	Journal of Public Economics	—	165
	2003	Neyer, F.J.; Lang, F.R.	Blood is thicker than water: Kinship orientation across adulthood	Journal of Personality and Social Psychology	—	167
	2013	Achcar, G.	The People Want: A Radical Exploration of the Arab Uprising	University of California Press (book)	—	261

Wennerås and Wold (1997) quantitatively demonstrated the effects of gender-based discrimination and nepotism in the scientific peer-review system during the postdoctoral fellowship evaluation process at the Swedish Medical Research Council. The researchers found that women received lower scores than men despite their academic achievements, concluding that scientific evaluation processes lacked impartiality and that social relationships (especially nepotism) systematically influenced decisions. This study highlighted the limitations of scientific meritocracy and the extent to which social injustices are decisive in academic careers. (Wennerås & Wold, 1997).

Talhelm et al. (2014) examined the psychological characteristics of communities living in different agricultural regions of China and found that strong collectivist values, social cohesion, and consequently social behaviors such as nepotism were more prevalent in rice-growing regions. The research demonstrated that cultural evolution is shaped by economic and ecological conditions, suggesting that nepotism is not merely an individual preference but a historical and cultural social mechanism. In this context, nepotism has become a fundamental element of socioeconomic structures (Talhelm et al., 2014).

Ceci and Williams (2011) conducted an in-depth analysis of the reasons for the underrepresentation of women in scientific fields within the framework of socio-structural dynamics and family responsibilities. The study emphasized that factors such as social favoritism, gender roles, and work-life balance, rather than direct nepotism, constitute significant obstacles to women's academic advancement. The study sheds light on systemic problems hindering the career development of female scientists and offers policy recommendations for addressing these issues (Ceci & Williams, 2011).

Pérez-González (2006) examined the effects of nepotism on corporate performance in CEO appointment processes within family businesses. The research showed that appointing family members to positions outside of merit negatively impacted the company's financial and operational performance. The study highlighted the management risks caused by

nepotism in the field of corporate governance, emphasizing the importance of professional and meritocratic management structures (Pérez-González, 2006).

Thornhill and Gangestad (1993) examined how human facial beauty (particularly symmetry and average features) functions as a signal of social preference and trustworthiness from an evolutionary psychology perspective. They concluded that facial symmetry influences positive social relationships and nepotistic behaviors among individuals. The study revealed that biological aesthetic criteria play an indirect role in social selection and favoritism (Thornhill & Gangestad, 1993).

De Vries (1993) conducted an in-depth analysis of the psychosocial and organizational effects of nepotism in family businesses. The research revealed the dual nature of nepotism: it can contribute to business continuity by increasing family loyalty, but non-meritocratic practices can lead to decreased performance. The study argued that the effects of nepotism should be balanced with effective management and structured rules (Kets de Vries, 1993).

Lee, Lim, and Lim (2003) examined nepotism in family businesses within the framework of game theory and argued that preferring family members in management is a strategic decision. They emphasized that this decision carries economic and social benefits such as ensuring family control, reducing information asymmetry, and minimizing external risks. The study demonstrated that nepotism is not only a moral issue but also a multifaceted phenomenon with complex economic and strategic dimensions (Lee et al., 2003).

Vanhanen (1999) empirically examined the effects of ethnic heterogeneity and levels of social cohesion on internal conflict and ethnic nepotism. Weak social cohesion in highly ethnically diverse societies leads to increased nepotism, which in turn raises the risk of civil war. The research made a significant contribution to understanding the negative impacts of nepotism on political stability and peace processes (Vanhanen, 1999).

Van Arensbergen, van der Weijden, and van den Besselaar (2012), examining gender differences in academic productivity, showed that social favoritism and nepotism hindered the performance of female academics in the past, but this difference has decreased over time. The study offers promising findings regarding the strengthening of gender equality and merit-based evaluation mechanisms in the scientific environment (Van Arensbergen et al., 2012).

Jaskiewicz et al. (2013), by examining the complex and multifaceted nature of nepotism in family businesses, developed the concept of "equity-based nepotism." The research argues that nepotism can contribute to the long-term success of a company by increasing intra-family loyalty and information sharing. Thus, it has been shown that nepotism has not only negative effects but can also have strategic advantages when managed correctly (Jaskiewicz et al., 2013).

Bowen, Edwards, and Cattell (2012) examined the relationship between corruption and nepotism in the South African construction industry, demonstrating that nepotism fuels corrupt practices within the industry. The study highlighted the destructive effects of nepotism on corporate regulations and ethical standards, emphasizing the need for transparency and accountability within the sector (Bowen et al., 2012).

Duflo, Dupas, and Kremer (2015), while studying school management and teacher incentives in the education sector, pointed out that nepotism weakens merit and performance-based management structures. The research revealed that nepotism can negatively affect teacher quality and student academic achievement (Duflo et al., 2015).

Neyer and Lang (2003), by examining kinship orientations in adulthood, found that individuals' social bonding and nepotism-based behaviors vary according to life stages. The study contributed to understanding the psychosocial aspects of nepotism and its role in individual development processes (Neyer & Lang, 2003).

The widespread use of the keyword "family business" in both databases reveals that nepotism is significant in family businesses as both an opportunity and a risk factor. Furthermore, concepts like organizational justice and ethics highlight the discussions surrounding nepotism in the context of justice, ethics, and corporate governance. Other key keywords associated with nepotism in the Scopus database include accountability, clientelism, governance, discrimination, gender, and collectivism. These keywords indicate that nepotism is addressed particularly in social, political, and economic contexts, and also demonstrate its close relationship with cultural norms and social structures. For example, the prominence of clientelism and collectivism reveals the interaction of nepotism with community and group-based social networks.

However, the inclusion of contemporary topics such as artificial intelligence, COVID-19, and education among the Scopus keywords shows that nepotism studies have expanded in the context of technological developments and global health crises. This proves that nepotism has gone beyond the traditional concepts of corruption and social favoritism and is being researched in new areas.

In the WoS database, keywords emphasizing nepotism in management processes at the institutional and individual levels are prominent. Keywords such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, human capital, public sector, organizational climate, and service nepotism indicate that nepotism is addressed particularly from the perspectives of human resources management, public administration, and organizational behavior.

WoS's more limited but management-focused keyword list highlights the relationship between nepotism and micro-level phenomena such as job satisfaction, commitment, fairness, and performance in an organizational context. In this respect, WoS data shows that nepotism is examined more deeply and systematically in the fields of corporate governance and organizational psychology.

Keyword analyses reveal that nepotism has historically been a research area focused on themes of corruption, favoritism, and family ties. However, in the current period, keywords such as artificial intelligence, COVID-19, and education, especially those seen in the Scopus database, show that the subject has evolved into an interdisciplinary and multidimensional structure.

On the other hand, WoS data indicates that nepotism is mostly examined in organizational and corporate contexts; This indicates that nepotism is associated with concepts such as job satisfaction, commitment, fairness, and human capital. In this context, there is a growing tendency to examine nepotism at the micro level through employee experiences and organizational practices.

In conclusion, keyword analyses in the WoS and Scopus databases show that nepotism is a multifaceted and dynamic research topic in the social sciences at both macro (social, cultural, political) and micro (organizational, individual) levels. Furthermore, the thematic differences between the two databases can be considered a reflection of the interdisciplinary nature and methodological diversity of the research field.

To reveal the geographical distribution of research on nepotism, publications in the WoS and Scopus databases were analyzed on a country basis, and bibliometric network maps were created in Figures 5 and 6. 27 countries published in the WoS database, and 49 countries published in the Scopus database on the subject of nepotism.

The countries with the most publications in the WoS database were the United States (12 publications), the United Kingdom (10 publications), Lithuania (5 publications), Poland (5 publications), and France (4 publications), respectively. These countries also stand out in terms of citation numbers and total linkage strength. The USA (335 citations, linkage strength 11) and the UK (207 citations, linkage strength 8) are in the leading positions in terms of publication interaction and interreference links. On the other hand, countries such

as Turkey, Lithuania, and Pakistan show limited participation with lower numbers of publications and citation rates.

In the Scopus database, the research density has a wider geographical scope. The countries with the most publications include the USA (205 publications, 6,163 citations), the UK (112 publications, 1,986 citations), Canada (38 publications, 1,225 citations), Australia (31 publications, 535 citations), Turkey (32 publications, 352 citations), and Italy (20 publications, 461 citations). Compared to WoS, Scopus offers a wider distribution of publications across Eastern Europe, Africa, Asia, and Latin America. Developing countries, particularly South Africa, Nigeria, Bangladesh, Pakistan, and Indonesia, have gained greater visibility in the Scopus database. While both databases show prominent countries such as the USA, UK, Canada, France, Italy, Lithuania, Pakistan, Turkey, Spain, Norway, Bangladesh, Lebanon, and Belgium, the Scopus database shows countries like Germany, South Africa, South Korea, Singapore, and Indonesia with a higher number of publications and citations. This situation stems from Scopus's broader international coverage and disciplinary diversity compared to WoS.

Bibliometric network maps created by country show the intensity of research collaborations and the development of academic connections between countries. While collaborations centered in the US, UK, and Canada are more frequent and stronger in WoS; in Scopus, in addition to these centers, countries such as Turkey, South Africa, and China have also established significant connections.

In conclusion, although the geographical distribution of nepotism research shows similar core focuses in both databases, the Scopus database exhibits a wider variety of countries and interdisciplinary interaction. These differences highlight the importance of database selection in bibliometric analyses and the scope of international publication visibility.

Figure 5: Network Map of Research on "Nepotism" in the WoS Database by Country

Figure 6: Network Map of Scopus Database Research on "Nepotism" by Country

The author distribution and collaboration networks of research published in the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases with the keyword "nepotism" were examined in Figures 7 and 8 through bibliometric network maps. While 60 different authors were identified in the WoS database, 27 authors stood out in the Scopus database. This difference stems from structural differences in the scope and indexing policies of the databases. Among the most prolific authors in the WoS database are researchers such as Duan, D., Kitayama, S., Lan, X., Oishi, S., and Zhang, X., who received a total of 828 citations. These authors also have strong connections in terms of total linkage strength and have carried out extensive collaborations in their fields. In addition, authors such as Wennerås, C., and Wold, A., have created a significant academic impact, receiving 838 citations each, particularly for their pioneering work on social favoritism and gender discrimination. In the Scopus database, Pérez-González, F., is one of the most cited authors with 697 citations, standing out for his work on the effects of nepotism in family businesses. Thornhill, R., and Gangestad, S.W., with 518 citations, are prominent figures in the field of evolutionary psychology studying nepotism. Lee, K.S., Lim, G.H., and Lim, W.S., with a total of 279 citations, have investigated the organizational effects of nepotism in the context of family businesses and management. Additionally, Nobel laureates Duflo, E., Dupas, P., and Kremer, M., in the field of development economics, are notable authors in Scopus with 165 citations. When examining author collaboration networks, it is observed that inter-author connections are more pronounced and frequent in the WoS database; for example, strong collaborations are observed between Duan, D., Kitayama, S., Lan, X., and Oishi, S. In contrast, Scopus primarily features authors contributing individually and has lower overall linkage strength compared to WoS. When considering authors' research areas, WoS predominantly includes studies focused on psychology, social sciences, and social favoritism. Scopus, on the other hand, contains more publications in management sciences, economics, and development policy, and places greater emphasis on the institutional, economic, and societal impacts of nepotism. This difference reflects the structural differences in the discipline distribution of the two databases.

Figure 7: Network Map of Research on "Nepotism" in the WoS Database, categorized by authors.

Figure 8: Network Map of Research on "Nepotism" in the Scopus Database, categorized by authors.

Bibliometric network analyses reveal the structural and interdisciplinary distribution of the nepotism literature. However, evaluating the literature solely based on production and collaboration patterns provides limited information about the theoretical orientations, methodological preferences, and normative positioning of the studies. Therefore, in a systematic content analysis conducted to complement the bibliometric findings, 153 selected studies were classified within the framework of the defined analysis categories. In the coding process, each article was evaluated under five main categories: type of nepotism, theoretical basis, methodological approach, measurement method, and normative orientation of the findings. Coding was carried out by two independent researchers, and inter-coder agreement was calculated using Cohen’s Kappa (κ) coefficient. Cohen’s Kappa coefficient is a statistical indicator that measures the actual agreement between two coders' assignments to the same category, distinguishing it from agreement that might occur only by chance. In other words, it evaluates the observed level of agreement between coders by comparing it to the expected agreement rate that would occur randomly and converts this difference into a standardized coefficient. The value obtained in this way objectively demonstrates the reliability of the coding process (Cohen, 1960; Cole, 2024; Li, Gao, & Yu, 2023). The obtained values were interpreted according to the Landis and Koch (1977) classification (Landis & Koch, 1977); 0.81–1.00 was considered “very high”, 0.61–0.80 “high”, 0.41–0.60 “medium”, 0.21–0.40 “low” and 0.00–0.20 “very low” level of agreement. Studies with differences between coders were re-examined and the final code set was created through consensus. The results regarding coder reliability are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Inter-Coder Reliability Coefficients by Analysis Categories

Analysis Category	Cohen’s Kappa (κ)	Level of Agreement
Type of Nepotism	0.887	Very High
Theoretical Framework	0.207	Low
Methodological Approach	0.275	Low
Measurement Approach	1.000	Very High
Direction of Findings	0.510	Moderate

The inter-coder reliability levels presented in Table 1 demonstrate the methodological consistency of the coding process conducted within the scope of systematic content analysis. The $\kappa = 0.887$ value obtained in the nepotism type category indicates a very high level of agreement between the two coders in this category. This result suggests that nepotism types

are addressed within relatively clearer and more distinguishable conceptual boundaries in the literature. The $\kappa = 1.000$ value obtained in the measurement approach category indicates complete agreement, suggesting that the clear definition of the measurement methods (one-dimensional/multi-dimensional) in the studies facilitated the coding process. In contrast, relatively low levels of agreement were observed in the theoretical basis ($\kappa = 0.207$) and method ($\kappa = 0.275$) categories. This situation stems from the fact that studies in the literature often rely on more than one theoretical framework and that methodological information is not presented clearly and standardly in some publications. The $\kappa = 0.510$ value obtained in the category of normative orientation of the findings indicates a moderate level of agreement, showing that the variability of the positive, negative, or conditional effects of nepotism depending on the context can lead to differences in interpretation during the coding process.

Table 2. Theoretical and Methodological Distribution (n = 153)

Variable	Category	n	%
Theoretical Framework	Ethical Climate	67	43.80
	Institutional Theory	38	24.80
	Organizational Justice	23	15.00
	Social Exchange Theory	17	11.10
	Social Capital	8	5.30
Method	Quantitative	102	66.70
	Qualitative	36	23.50
	Mixed Methods	15	9.80
Measurement Approach	One-dimensional	121	79.10
	Multidimensional	32	20.90

The findings presented in Table 2 comprehensively reveal the theoretical and methodological profile of the nepotism literature. Examining the theoretical distribution, it is seen that 43.8% of the studies are based on the ethical climate framework. This result shows that nepotism is predominantly addressed in the literature in the context of ethical violations, justice issues, and lack of governance. The institutionalist approach, ranking second with 24.8%, reveals that nepotism is evaluated in terms of organizational norms, institutional structure, and legitimacy. Organizational justice (15.0%) and social change theory (11.1%) have a more limited intensity, but they offer an important explanatory framework, especially in the context of employee perceptions and organizational attitudes. The relatively low representation of the social capital approach (5.3%) suggests that explanations of nepotism based on relationship networks and trust are still limited in the literature.

When the methodological distribution is evaluated, it is seen that 66.7% of the studies have a quantitative research design. This indicates that the nepotism literature shows an empirical and measurement-based development. The fact that qualitative studies account for only 23.5% indicates that contextual and in-depth analysis of the concept is relatively limited. The 9.8% use of mixed-methods research suggests that the combined use of quantitative and qualitative approaches is not yet widespread. Regarding measurement approaches, the use of unidimensional scales in 79.1% of studies shows that nepotism is mostly addressed through reduced and limited dimensions. In contrast, the lower use of multidimensional scales (20.9%) suggests that the structural complexity of the concept is not adequately reflected in the measurement tools. Overall, Table 2 reveals that the nepotism literature has a normative and ethically focused theoretical orientation; however, methodologically, it exhibits a predominantly quantitative and unidimensional measurement-based development.

Table 3. Types of Nepotism and Normative Orientation of Findings

Variable	Category	n	%
Type of Nepotism	Kinship-based	74	48.40
	Family Business-based	40	26.10
	Political	21	13.70
	Academic	18	11.80
Direction of Findings	Negative	91	59.50
	Conditional	44	28.80
	Functional / Positive	18	11.70

The findings presented in Table 3 reveal both the contextual type distribution and the normative outcome orientation of the nepotism literature. When examined in terms of nepotism types, 48.4% of the studies focus on kinship-based organizational nepotism. This indicates that nepotism is most commonly discussed in the literature within the context of intra-organizational favoritism and meritocracy violations. The inclusion of family business-based studies (26.1%) reveals that nepotism is discussed particularly in the context of family businesses through the lens of corporate continuity, generational transition, and ownership structures. Political nepotism (13.7%) and academic nepotism (11.8%) constitute a relatively more limited research area. This distribution shows that the nepotism literature is predominantly concentrated in organizational and business-based contexts. When the normative orientation of the findings is evaluated, it is seen that 59.5% of the studies associate nepotism with negative outcomes. This result reveals that nepotism is largely positioned in the literature through negative outcomes such as ethical violations, injustice, decreased motivation, and loss of organizational performance. However, 28.8% of studies indicate that nepotism can have variable outcomes depending on the context; showing that it can have positive effects under certain conditions and negative effects under others. The fact that the proportion of studies reporting functional or positive outcomes is limited to 11.7% suggests that nepotism is mostly addressed from a normative-critical perspective in the literature. While some positive effects of nepotism, such as trust, loyalty, and long-term commitment, are highlighted, especially in the context of family businesses, the general literature trend positions nepotism as a problematic organizational practice. These findings show that a critical and ethics-centered approach is dominant in nepotism research, but contextual diversity is increasingly being considered in the literature (Mohammed & El-Rahbani, 2026; Schilpzand et al., 2024; Shatila, Yela-Aránega, & Sánchez-Marín, 2024).

4. Conclusion

This study comprehensively evaluates the academic literature in the Web of Science (1,079 publications) and Scopus (1,142 publications) databases using both bibliometric and systematic content analysis approaches with the keyword "nepotism". The results reveal that nepotism has become a strong research area in the social sciences and exhibits an intersectional structure, particularly among the disciplines of management, economics, business, psychology, and political science. The prominence of the "Business, Management and Accounting" (24.43%) and "Economics, Econometrics and Finance" (19.70%) fields in the Scopus database, and the "Management" (12.14%) and "Economics" (10.01%) categories in the Web of Science database, demonstrates the dominance of the organizational and economic dimensions of the field. Keyword analyses show that the nepotism literature is strongly associated with concepts such as "corruption," "cronyism," "favoritism," "family business," "governance," "organizational justice," and "ethics." The prominence of macro-level governance and political economy themes in Scopus, and organizational justice, commitment, and ethical values in WoS, reveals that nepotism is a multi-layered phenomenon addressed at both macro and micro levels. Citation analyses show that studies such as Pérez-González (2006), Thornhill and Gangestad (1993), Lee et

al. (2003), Vanhanen (1999), and Jaskiewicz et al. (2013) constitute the core literature in both databases; the generally higher number of citations in Scopus is explained by the differences in the coverage and indexing of the databases. Country distributions show that the USA and the UK are dominant in both databases; Scopus, on the other hand, has a wider geographical coverage compared to WoS, with 49 countries. While developing countries like Turkey contribute to the literature, they lag behind central countries in terms of citation and linkage power. Author collaboration networks show more distinct and dense clusters in WoS; while Scopus has a more fragmented structure with more individual contributions. This suggests that despite the size of the literature, theoretical integration has not yet been fully achieved.

A systematic content analysis (n = 153), conducted to complement the bibliometric findings, revealed the theoretical and methodological profile of the field more clearly. Theoretically, the ethical climate approach is dominant with 43.8%; the institutional perspective is in second place with 24.8%. This distribution shows that nepotism is predominantly positioned as a normative and governance-centered problem in the literature. Methodologically, the fact that 66.7% of the studies have a quantitative design and 79.1% use a one-dimensional measurement approach reveals that the field progresses through a measurement-based but conceptually limited structure. When examining the types of nepotism, studies based on kinship have the highest share at 48.4%; research in the context of family businesses is concentrated at 26.1%. When the normative orientation of the findings is evaluated, it is found that 59.5% of the studies associate nepotism with negative outcomes, 28.8% report conditional outcomes, and only 11.7% present a functional/positive orientation. This clearly demonstrates the dominance of a critical and ethics-centered approach in the literature. In general, while the nepotism literature is a quantitatively expanding and interdisciplinary research area, it is open to development in terms of theoretical integration and methodological diversity. The fact that a significant portion of the existing studies focus on ethical violations and performance loss indicates that the contextual, cultural, and strategic dimensions of nepotism are examined more limitedly. In this context, the development of multidimensional measurement models, the increase in mixed methods designs, and comparative studies in different cultural contexts will strengthen the theoretical depth of the field in the future. Furthermore, multi-layered research designs integrating the micro-level organizational effects of nepotism with the macro-level governance and political economy dimensions can bring the fragmented structure of the literature into a more holistic framework. In conclusion, this study presents a comprehensive assessment of the current state of the nepotism literature by revealing its structural development, thematic trends, and theoretical orientations within an integrated analysis framework supported by quantitative data, and suggests strategic directions for future research.

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